

“EVALUATION OF BRINJAL ROOTSTOCKS FOR GROWTH AND YIELD IN TOMATO”

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Abstract:

The present investigation was conducted to study the compatibility of tomato grafted on wild brinjal rootstock with an objective to study the effect of rootstock on growth, yield and graft success (%) in tomato. The study was carried out at the Farm of Dr. Sharadchandra Pawar College of Agriculture, Baramati during kharif season 2023-24. The experimental material consisting of seventeen brinjal rootstocks and one tomato scion in a Randomized Block Design (RBD) with 3 replications and eighteen treatments. The results revealed that Meghdoot grafted on SMR-15 showed highest graft success rate (98.00%) with maximum crop duration of 195.00 days. The results showed significant increase in average fruit weight (103.60 g), polar diameter (6.54 cm), number of fruits per plant (51.40), yield per plant (5.33 kg), yield per plot (74.56 kg) and yield per hectare (98.62 t/ha). It is concluded that Meghdoot grafted on SMR-15 was found suitable for better growth and yield as it significantly increased the better growth, higher graft success, maximum crop duration, average fruit weight, number of fruits per plant and yield per plant.

Key Words: Grafting, Tomato, Fusarium wilt, Rootstock, Growth, Yield

Introduction:

Tomato (*Solanum Lycopersicon* L.) is a member of the Solanaceae family and is one of the most significant vegetable crops grown all over the world due to its nutritional and economic importance. It has a diploid chromosome number $2n=24$. Originating in Peru, South America, it has spread worldwide and is cultivated in fields, greenhouses and net houses (Wener, 2000). Tomato holds a prominent place among protective foods due to they are abundant with minerals such as calcium (48 mg per 100g), sodium (12.9 mg) and trace elements like copper (0.19 mg) as well as their excellent source of vitamins, including vitamin A (900 IU), vitamin C (27 mg) and vitamin B complex like thiamine. Also, tomatoes contain essential amino acids and beneficial organic acids, including citric, formic and acetic acids (Tiwari *et al.*, 2022).

Grafting is a method in which the shoots of two independent plants of the same or different species are physically joined together and developed as one plant. (Traka- Mavrona *et al.*, 2000). The fundamental advantage of grafted plants is that the root system is stronger and more efficient in absorbing of water and nutrients, which indirectly boosts production. (Edelstein *et al.*, 2017; Savvas *et al.*, 2010; Schwarz *et al.*, 2010). According to recent studies, grafting was a useful technique to improve nutrient uptake, yield, disease resistance and stress tolerance due to the rootstock's robust root system. (Miskovic *et al.*, 2008, Kowalczyk and Gajc-Wolska, 2011). To meet the ever-increasing needs of consumers, increased production and product quality are essential. Abiotic and biotic stressors are also major constraints in production of tomato. Chemical treatments are also accessible for dealing with these biotic and abiotic stressors. However, chemicals can be harmful not just to consumer health but also to the farmer himself (Sen *et al.*, 2018). As a result, there is a pressing need to discover an alternate strategy to address these issues, grafting is another method. Vegetable grafting has emerged as a promising and practical alternative to traditional breeding methods for increasing resistance to both biotic and abiotic stresses (Schwarz *et al.*, 2010, Malhotra, 2017). It allows some genetic variants of specific species to be transferred and phenotype of scion are influenced by rootstock characteristics (Lee *et al.*, 2010). Grafting proves to be an effective strategy for controlling soil borne diseases, while also enhancing growth vigor, fruit yield and overall quality (Sabatino *et al.*, 2016).

There is inadequate information available regarding the plant growth characteristics, yield as well as fruit quality of tomatoes grafted onto wild brinjal rootstock (Black *et al.*, 2003). Hence, it is important to investigate how tomatoes respond in terms of growth and yield when grafted onto wild brinjal rootstock. The purpose of the present investigation is to evaluate the effects of various brinjal rootstocks on growth, yield and disease incidence in tomato.

Hence, this experiment was conducted with an objective to study the compatibility of tomato grafted on wild brinjal rootstocks for growth and yield.

Materials and Methods:

The present investigation was carried out at the Dr. Sharadchandra Pawar College of Agriculture, Baramati during kharif season of 2023-24. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design (RBD) with 18 treatments and 3 replications with plot size of 2.74 m × 3.20 m. The grafted tomato seedlings were transplanted at recommended spacing of 120 cm × 45 cm.

The nursery of rootstocks and scion were raised in protrays having uniform size and cells of equal size using soil-less media (cocopeat: perlite: vermiculite) in the ratio of 3:1:1, respectively in the growth chamber. One seed was sown per cell by making small depression (0.5 cm) with finger so as to ensure that seed is kept in the centre of cell. Seeds of brinjal rootstocks and tomato scion were sown in protrays having 104 small cells. Water was sprayed initially through rose can and trays were covered with polythene sheet so that seeds do not come outside. Trays were regularly monitored and checked and on emergence of germination the polythene sheet was removed. All the necessary precautions were taken for raising healthy seedlings. Rootstocks were sown one week earlier than scion so that the diameter of both the stems matches with each other for ensuring successful grafting.

Splice grafting method was used for grafting in this experiment when the scion and rootstock seedlings attained their desired height and girth. 1.6 mm silicon clips were used for grafting. Grafted plants were placed in a healing chamber to maximise grafting success. To allow the graft union, they were kept in healing chambers with relative humidity of 85-90% and temperatures ranging from 28-32°C for five to six days. Graft union was secured with a grafting clip to ensure good vascular connection and to ensure complete healing of grafted portions. Grafted plants were planted to find its effect on growth, yield and quality. The observations were recorded for rootstock, scion and grafts combination with respect to graft success, crop duration, growth and yield related parameters on brinjal rootstock. The data obtained for different treatments under investigation was subjected to statistical analysis as per procedure prescribed for Randomized Block Design (RBD) as suggested by Panse and Sukhatme (1985).

Result and Discussion:

Grafting success (%):

The results revealed that there was considerable variation between the graft success which ranged from 87.00% to 98.00%. The maximum grafting success rate was obtained in Meghdoot grafted on SMR-15 (98.00%) which was at par with Meghdoot grafted on SMR-10 (97.50%), Meghdoot grafted on SMR-9 (96.50%) and Meghdoot grafted on SMR-2 (96.33%). While, the minimum graft success was noted in Meghdoot grafted on SMR-13 (87.00%). The highest grafting success rate was recorded in Meghdoot grafted on SMR-15 (Table 1). This might be the result of better graft union and favorable conditions provided in the healing chamber. The results agree with the findings of Rashid *et al.*, (2004), Mohammed *et al.*, (2009), Rathod (2017) and Chandanshive *et al.*, (2023).

Days to first flowering:

The minimum number of days required for initiation of flowering (30.22) was recorded in Meghdoot grafted on SMR-15, while the maximum number of days was recorded in Meghdoot grafted on SMR-13 (35.78) (Table 1). The grafted plants flowered earlier because of the use of efficient, improved and vigorous rootstocks, which may have resulted in increased water as well as nutrient uptake than non-grafted plants. The above finding is consistent with results reported by Mahbou *et al.*, (2022).

Days to 50% flowering:

The Meghdoot grafted on SMR-15 recorded lowest number of days required for 50% flowering (38.00). Whereas, Meghdoot grafted on SMR-13 (46.00) required the highest number of days to 50% flowering (Table 1). The results of this study indicated that grafted plants flower earlier than non-grafted plants. The above results are in accordance with results reported by Nkansanh *et al.*, (2013), Kumar *et al.*, (2019) and Chandanshive *et al.*, (2023).

Number of primary branches/plants:

The maximum number of branches per plant (7.33) at harvest was recorded in Meghdoot grafted on SMR-15. Whereas, the lowest branches per plant was noticed in Meghdoot grafted on SMR-13 (5.22)

(Table 1). The vigorous root system of the rootstock enhanced vigorous growth of scion which was resulted in a greater number of branches in grafted plants. The above findings are consistent with Chandanshive *et al.*, (2023), Salehi-Mohammadi *et al.*, (2009) and Rathod (2017).

Days to first harvesting:

The Meghdoot grafted on SMR-15 recorded the lowest number of days for first harvesting (72.00 days), whereas the highest number of days was recorded in the graft combination of Meghdoot grafted on SMR-13 (77.67 days) (Table 1). These findings consistent with the Soe *et al.*, (2018), Nkansanh *et al.*, (2013) and Chandanshive *et al.*, (2023).

Crop duration (days):

The data revealed that Meghdoot grafted onto SMR-15 recorded longer crop duration (195.00 days). Whereas, shorter crop duration was observed from Control (non-grafted) i.e. 160.67 days (Table 1). This could be due to increased water as well as nutrient uptake by robust rootstock, improved stomatal conductance, which leads to increased crop growth, regulated uptake, synthesis as well as translocation of water, minerals and plant hormones and increased photosynthate production. These results align with the findings of Subba *et al.*, (2021) and Chandanshive *et al.*, (2023).

Table 1 Effect of grafting of tomato on brinjal rootstock for growth characters

Treatment	Treatment details	Grafting success (%)	Days to first flowering	Days to 50% flowering	No. of primary branches/plant	Days to first harvesting	Crop duration (days)
T ₁	Meghdoot/SMR-1	94.00	34.00	44.33	5.44	75.00	179.67
T ₂	Meghdoot/SMR-2	96.33	31.56	40.67	6.33	74.00	186.67
T ₃	Meghdoot/SMR-3	88.33	34.11	44.67	5.33	75.67	179.00
T ₄	Meghdoot/SMR-4	92.67	33.55	42.00	5.78	74.67	181.67
T ₅	Meghdoot/SMR-5	94.00	34.00	43.00	5.67	75.33	180.11
T ₆	Meghdoot/SMR-6	94.67	33.00	41.67	5.89	74.67	183.33
T ₇	Meghdoot/SMR-7	93.50	31.78	40.67	6.33	73.67	186.33
T ₈	Meghdoot/SMR-8	90.00	35.55	45.33	5.33	75.67	178.33
T ₉	Meghdoot/SMR-9	96.50	31.00	39.33	6.44	73.67	189.33
T ₁₀	Meghdoot/SMR-10	97.50	30.67	39.00	7.11	73.33	192.11
T ₁₁	Meghdoot/SMR-11	95.33	33.11	42.33	5.89	74.67	182.67
T ₁₂	Meghdoot/SMR-12	94.50	33.00	41.67	6.00	74.33	183.33
T ₁₃	Meghdoot/SMR-13	87.00	35.78	46.00	5.22	77.67	177.67
T ₁₄	Meghdoot/SMR-14	93.67	31.22	39.67	6.67	73.67	187.00
T ₁₅	Meghdoot/SMR-15	98.00	30.22	38.00	7.33	72.00	195.00
T ₁₆	Meghdoot/SMR-16	92.00	32.33	42.00	6.11	74.33	184.11
T ₁₇	Meghdoot/SMR-17	93.33	32.11	41.67	6.22	74.00	184.33
T ₁₈	Control	-	33.78	42.00	5.67	75.00	160.67
	S.E. (m) ±	0.85	0.95	1.23	0.29	0.85	1.38
	CD at 5%	2.46	2.74	3.53	0.84	2.45	3.97

Fig. 1 Effect of grafting of tomato on brinjal rootstock for growth characters

Polar diameter (cm):

The highest polar diameter was recorded in Meghdoot grafted on SMR-15 (6.54 cm). While, the lowest polar diameter was noticed in the Meghdoot grafted on SMR-11 (5.62 cm) (Table 2). The grafted plants showed higher polar diameter of fruit than the non-grafted plants. The increase in fruit length could be a result of the rootstock

and scion compatibility, which results in better nutrient and water absorption. The above results in tune with the results of Rathod (2017), Singh *et al.*, (2019), Hossain *et al.*, (2019) and Chandanshive *et al.*, (2023).

Equatorial diameter (cm):

The maximum equatorial diameter was observed in Meghdoot grafted on SMR-9 (5.25 cm). Whereas, the minimum equatorial diameter was observed in Meghdoot grafted on SMR-3 (4.68 cm) (Table 2). These findings are analogous to the findings of Soe *et al.*, (2018), Singh *et al.*, (2019), Hossain *et al.*, (2019) and Chandanshive *et al.*, (2023).

Number of fruits/ plants:

The highest number of fruits per plant was recorded in Meghdoot grafted on SMR-15 (51.40), whereas the least number of fruits was recorded in Meghdoot grafted on SMR-13 (38.17) (Table 2). Favorable climatic conditions, crop duration, varietal characteristics, vigorous rootstock and rootstock-scion compatibility may all contribute to the maximum number of fruits per plant. The above results are in accordance with results reported by Turhan *et al.*, (2011) and Chandanshive *et al.*, (2023).

Average fruit weight (g):

The highest average fruit weight was observed in Meghdoot grafted on SMR-15 (103.60 g). Whereas, the lowest average fruit weight was reported in Meghdoot grafted on SMR-13 (83.77 g) (Table 2). The increased average fruit weight noticed in grafted plants may be attributed to interactions between rootstocks and scions, which can result in more efficient mineral, water and nutrient uptake throughout the plant system. The above findings are in accordance with results described by Turhan *et al.*, (2011), Ahmed (2014) and Ibrahim (2014).

Yield/ plant (kg):

Table 2 Effect of grafting of tomato on brinjal rootstock for yield characters

Treatment	Treatment details	Polar diameter (cm)	Equatorial diameter (cm)	No. of fruits/plant	Av. fruit weight (g)	Yield/plant (kg)	Yield/plot (kg)	Yield/hectare (t)
T ₁	Meghdoot/SMR-1	6.35	5.05	40.75	92.70	3.78	52.93	70.02
T ₂	Meghdoot/SMR-2	5.95	4.81	45.67	95.29	4.35	60.83	80.47
T ₃	Meghdoot/SMR-3	6.12	4.68	40.56	92.06	3.74	52.36	69.26
T ₄	Meghdoot/SMR-4	5.87	4.75	42.61	93.20	3.97	55.58	73.52
T ₅	Meghdoot/SMR-5	6.23	5.03	41.89	92.88	3.89	54.50	72.08
T ₆	Meghdoot/SMR-6	5.99	4.77	43.52	93.38	4.07	56.95	75.34
T ₇	Meghdoot/SMR-7	6.07	4.98	45.31	95.00	4.30	60.16	79.57
T ₈	Meghdoot/SMR-8	5.66	4.92	39.11	85.77	3.34	46.83	61.94
T ₉	Meghdoot/SMR-9	6.10	5.25	47.80	98.71	4.72	66.05	87.37
T ₁₀	Meghdoot/SMR-10	6.49	5.16	50.10	101.37	5.07	71.05	93.98
T ₁₁	Meghdoot/SMR-11	5.62	4.82	44.34	93.84	4.16	58.30	77.12
T ₁₂	Meghdoot/SMR-12	5.83	4.78	44.95	94.10	4.22	59.06	78.12
T ₁₃	Meghdoot/SMR-13	6.04	4.70	38.17	83.77	3.20	44.83	59.30
T ₁₄	Meghdoot/SMR-14	6.14	4.85	47.65	95.78	4.57	63.91	84.54
T ₁₅	Meghdoot/SMR-15	6.54	5.12	51.40	103.60	5.33	74.56	98.62
T ₁₆	Meghdoot/SMR-16	6.25	5.10	45.04	94.60	4.26	59.68	78.94
T ₁₇	Meghdoot/SMR-17	5.91	5.01	45.23	94.65	4.27	59.82	79.13
T ₁₈	Control	6.17	4.87	39.67	90.23	3.58	50.09	66.26
	S.E. (m) ±	0.12	0.11	2.06	2.79	0.18	2.52	3.34
	CD at 5%	0.35	0.32	5.93	8.03	0.51	7.25	9.60

Conclusion:

The present study revealed that Meghdoot grafted on SMR-15 was found suitable for better growth and yield as it significantly increased the better growth, higher graft success, maximum crop duration, average fruit weight, number of fruits per plant and yield per plant. Hence, the graft combination of Meghdoot grafted on SMR-15 shows potential for further evaluation and promotion in cultivation.

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The highest fruit yield per plant was observed in Meghdoot grafted on SMR-15 (5.33 kg), while the lowest fruit yield per plant was found in Meghdoot grafted on SMR-13 rootstock (3.20 kg) (Table 2). These findings align with Turhan *et al.*, (2011), Soe *et al.*, (2018), Hossain *et al.*, (2019), and Chandanshive *et al.*, (2023), who described that fruit yield per plant was maximum in grafted plants than non-grafted plants.

Yield/ plot (kg):

The highest fruit yield per plot was occurred in Meghdoot grafted on SMR-15 (74.56 kg) (Table 2). However, the least fruit yield per plot was found in the Meghdoot grafted on SMR-13 (44.83 kg). These results are in harmony with the findings of Chandanshive *et al.*, (2023).

Yield/ hectare (t):

The maximum fruit yield per hectare was noticed in Meghdoot grafted on SMR-15 (98.62 t). Although, the minimum fruit yield per ha was found in the Meghdoot grafted on SMR-13 (59.30 t) (Table 2). Higher yield in grafted plants is attributed to rootstock resistance to soil-borne diseases, improved absorption also translocation of phosphorus, nitrogen, magnesium and calcium which leads to better nutrient uptake as rootstocks having well developed and robust root systems that release more cytokinins into the xylem sap resulting in increased yield and also due to increased rate of photosynthesis. These results are parallel with the findings of Nkansanh *et al.*, (2013), Hossain *et al.*, (2019) and Chandanshive *et al.*, (2023).

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Fig.2 Effect of grafting of tomato on brinjal rootstock for yield characters